

THE ROLE OF GAMES AND ACTIVITIES IN ENHANCING LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

Xalilova Nodira

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

English Philology Faculty

***Annotation.** In our globalized world, it is becoming critical to master foreign languages for people regardless of their age categories. In this article, the author explores the types of games applied in the primary school classrooms in order to develop lexical competence among pupils from an early stage of their education path.*

***Key words.** Lexical knowledge, vocabulary, context, games, interactive, problem-solving, critical -thinking.*

Introduction. The term "lexical competence" is a set of lexical knowledge, skills and competencies that determine students' ability to find contextual meaning of a word, compare its meaning in two languages and use the word in an appropriate context. Why is lexical competence important for primary school learners. There are a couple of reasons why primary school pupils require mastering lexical competence, firstly, since they commence learning a new language, vocabulary is a core of every language. Therefore, there is a high demand on developing lexical ability as early as possible in students. It is evident that without grammar little can be expressed, but without words nothing can be explained in communication, education and other domains.

In today's globalized era, it is of great significance to master at least one foreign language from childhood in order to provide themselves with high job prospects, career opportunities and bright future. Thus, language learning requires different skills, techniques and activities to accelerate the learning process in a short term. Additionally, those languages can be mastered through paying enough

attention to vocabulary basis of the languages, as words comprise the whole language.

Since we started turning into a modern lifestyle, our way of getting instruction has been changed. It means that communicative language teaching, task-based approaches, learner-centred approaches play an integral role in teaching sphere. Among them, games are crucially vital to boost lexical competence among learners. There are several types of games that are commonly applied in the classrooms of primary schools by well-experienced teachers. For example,

1. Matching Game

Level: Grade 1 to 5

Skills Reinforced: To describing or defining words; Vocabulary Development

Materials: pictures, large piece of paper, pencil.

Procedure: Prepare a set of flashcards for each target vocabulary a large piece of paper on the wall for each group to tick their work later. Ask the groups to match the flashcards. Give the key to each group so they can peer-check the other group`s work.

2. Guess Game

Level: Grade 3 to 5

Skills Reinforced: To finding new vocabulary within quick thinking, remembering new vocabulary

Materials: board, pencil.

Procedure: Ask a student to write a newly learnt word in the middle of the board. Think of a word, which shares a letter with the word on board, and give students a clue to your word. If somebody guesses the word, she/he writes the word so it crosses the word and shares a letter.

3. Crossword Puzzle

Level: Grade 2 to 5

Skills Reinforced: To finding new vocabulary with remembering

Material: None

Procedure: It contains a number of arranged squares. The goal of this game is to fill the white squares with letters. These words are the response of a number of provided clues. It can be helpful in vocabulary practice, level, and the course objectives. Even, vocabulary is extension.

To sum up, games are fun activities that promote interaction, thinking, learning, and problem-solving strategies either a game is a system in which players engage in an artificial conflict, defined by rules that results in a qualifiable outcome. Especially, regarding lexical competence as stated above games are considered to be of great importance in teaching vocabulary in a fun way. The reason for relying on games as an instructional tool, primary school learners poses a short attention span around 15-20minutes, and this time is spent for new lesson explanation, the other time they must play an engaging games or fun activities to motivate pupils to continue learning till they achieve an intended result or success, eventually.

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